

Lead of the Quality of University Education According to Strategic Planning. An Exploratory Research for a Sample of Faculties of the University of Baghdad

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Abstract—The Study is based on two variables, the strategic planning, and lead of quality of university education. Both the concepts were presented intellectually followed by an examination of the extent of the impact of the strategic planning is described as an independent variable in pioneering the quality of university education of Iraq. The research aims at finding out how to strategically plan for the university educational institutions in accordance with the requirements of quality pioneering. Also, the importance of research emerges from the fact that quality is counted as a pioneering way of improving the university educational system and developing it in the light of strategic planning. The University of Baghdad was selected as the community of the research; the research sample highlighted the professors and leaders present in deanships of colleges of Business and Economics, Faculty of Law and faculty of Physical Education for women of (65) people. A questionnaire has been designed and distributed to the research sample. After analysis, it was confirmed that most of the sub-variables of the study were effective while some of them showed a decline. Also, the positive and negative aspects in the strategic planning process were stood upon and came up with recommendations and mechanisms of action aims to develop goals and strategies to achieve the vision of the University of Baghdad in the provision of educational service of high quality.

Index Terms-- Lead of quality, Strategic planning, University Education, Strategic Leadership, Pioneering work teams, Proactivity.

I. METHODOLOGY of RESEARCH

A. Research Problem

The topic of strategic planning as an ideology and philosophy has been researched by the strategists in the institutions of university education. It is possible to implement the concept of pioneering of quality by the university administrations through strategic planning of educational institutions.

From here comes the problem of the study represented in answering the following main question:

How is it possible to develop the university education for the development of Iraqi society using the methods of pioneering of quality in accordance with strategic planning?

From the main problem of the research, two subsidiary questions are derived:

- a. Do the supreme administrations take into consideration the pioneering of performance quality when setting the strategic plans? Or the planning comes as a response to timely urgent necessities that are not related to achieving the quality of university performance.
- b. What are the reflections of strategic planning adopted currently at the University of Baghdad on the pioneering of its quality of education?

B. Objectives of the Research

The research aims at achieving the following objectives:

- a. Acknowledging the requirements of implementation of pioneering of quality in university education system.
- b. Throwing the light at the most important elements of strategic planning to draw a path and direction for university education.
- c. Clarification of the relationship between the pioneering of quality of education and strategic planning in university education.
- d. Stating the influence of strategic planning in pioneering the quality of education.

C. The Importance of Research

The importance of the research appears through highlighting the following:

- a. The importance of the introduction of pioneering of total quality management as a method of improving the university education system and developing it in the light of strategic planning.
- b. The contribution of pioneering of quality of education in accordance with the strategic planning in strengthening the relationship between the university and the local society through increasing cooperation for the service of this society.

D. The methodology of the Research

The descriptive analytical method was adopted as the research methodology in analyzing the concept of pioneering of education quality and the requirement of its implementation in the universities, the factors affecting it and the reality of Iraqi universities in the potential of implementing it in order to improve its educational outputs that will positively reflect upon the development of the society and the obstacles of its implementation.

E. Research Measurement Tool

After a review of the management and strategy literature, the research measurement was formulated and constructed using two main variables (Strategic Planning and Pioneering of Quality). The first variable consists of five subsidiary dimensions (strategic leadership, strategic analysis of environment, vision, mission and objectives of the educational institution, ability to make strategic decisions, creative thinking by the planner). Whereas the second variable pioneering of education quality has the following subsidiary dimensions (Support and commitment of higher administration, pioneering work team, Independence, Proactivity, continuous improvement). As shown in the table below:

Table (1) Research Measurement Tool

Main Variables	Dimensions	Researcher and Year	Clauses
Strategic Planning	Strategic Planning	National Commission for Academic Evaluation and Accreditation, Quality Assurance and Accreditation Standards for Higher Education Institutions, November 2009	7
	Strategic Analysis of Environment	Prepared by the researchers based on scientific literature	4
	Vision, message and goals of educational institution	Muslih: 2010	7
	Making the strategic decision	Prepared by the researcher depending on the scientific literature	5
	Creative thinking of the thinker	The researcher depending upon (National Commission for Academic Evaluation and Accreditation, Quality Assurance and Accreditation Standards for Higher Education Institutions, November 2009)	10
The Leadership of Quality Education	Support and commitment of higher management	Laith Shakir: 2012, Mohammed Alnuaimi: 2005)	5
	Leading work team	researchers depending on Robin et al. (2005) Mohammed: 2011	5
	Independence	Alhasnawi: 2010	5
	Proactivity	Dawood: 2011, Alhasnawi: 2010	5
	Continuous improvement	Falah: 2014, Barakat: 2007	5

F. Research Hypotheses

Based on the research problem and with the help of the presentations of previous studies, we can identify the hypotheses and sub-hypothesis as follows:

Table (2): Hypotheses and Sub-hypothesis

Hypothesis	Sub Hypothesis	
H1		A real acceptable relationship exists between the strategic planning and quality pioneering in the frame of the present environment.
	H1.1	The dimensions of strategic planning are positively related to the quality pioneering of university education.
H2		The strength of strategic planning increases in creating the effective quality for the successful educational institution.
H3		The impact of the dimensions of strategic planning increases in strength in creating the effective quality for the successful educational institution.

The questionnaire was finally formulated in the light of intellectual and strategic literature in the field of strategic planning and total quality management. It was then distributed over the employees of the college of economics, college of law, college of physical education in Baghdad University. The credibility of the reliability coefficient was extracted to confirm the solid correlation between the credibility of the test and its validity, in addition to the extraction of the validity of the questionnaire with the coefficient (Alpha Gron – Back) which amounted to (918.%), consequently, the credibility of the measure (95%) represents an excellent reliability coefficient percentage wise.

G. Research Community and Sample

The University of Baghdad was selected as the research community, as it is one of the prestigious universities with outstanding performance in the scientific environment in the country. The colleges of administration and economics, law and physical education for women were selected for the ease of obtaining the information and data.

The table below shows the personal data of the research sample. It is noticed that the highest proportion was of girls, the highest age group was of the young group (36-40) and (41-45). In addition to the educational qualification in which the majority of members were of master degree holders, also most of the sample had a job service of 11 – 15 years.

Table (3) Research Sample

II.

Sex	Repetitions	Repetitions	Percentage
Male	21	21	32.3
Female	44	44	67.7
Total	65	65	100.0
Age Group	Repetitions	Repetitions	Percentage
35-30	4	4	6.2
40-36	23	23	35.4
45-41	23	23	35.4
50-46	12	12	18.5
51 and above	3	3	4.6
Total	65	65	100.0
Scientific Qualification	Repetitions	Repetitions	Percentage
Master	42	42	64.6
PhD	23	23	35.4
Total	65	65	100.0
Total Service	Repetitions	Repetitions	Percentage
Less than five years	12	12	18.5
10-6	7	7	10.8
15-11	41	41	63.1
20-16	3	3	4.6
25-21	1	1	1.5
26 and above	1	1	1.5
total	65	65	100.0
Scientific title or job position			
professor	8	12.3	12.3
Associate Professor	16	24.6	36.9
Assistant teacher	16	24.6	61.5
Teacher	11	16.9	78.5
Unit Administrator	13	20.0	98.5
Head of Department	1	1.5	100.0
	65	100.0	

I.

assen & Potman: 2005) entitled “strategic planning for higher education: Netherland.”

Study Objective: Establishment of a system for higher education which has more diversity, flexibility, and adaptability that depends upon institutional distinction on the basis of the strategic preference of the institution.

Study Methodology: Analytical description was adopted through the research tool “the questionnaire” for the measurement of the appropriateness of samples.

Study Results: The illustrative sample is considered the best for implementation in higher education foundations.

2. A study by Werkolla: 2007 “Humanitarian scenarios for strategic planning: a living experiment of the dean of Research Community University at Minnesota

Study Objectives: Exploring the process of strategic planning in higher education

through the description and analysis of the experiments of colleges deans and their direct participation in it.

Study Methodology: Analytical description and interviews with deans of colleges.

Study Community: The study community is composed of 15 deans who introduced their deepened views of the planning process and the role of academic leadership in it.

Study Results: The strategic thinking comes at the forefront of the strategic planning process, and that the intellectual change of the general identity represents a primary strategy to stimulate the material and structural change. The academic leadership should be integrated completely and continuously in the strategic thinking and reactions among individuals.

3. *A study by (Defifo: 2008) entitled "Strategic planning: an analysis in two small colleges in the United States of America."*

Study Objective: The diagnosis of the process of strategic planning and its role in building confidence relation in the process of decision making and the role that must be performed by the dean of the college in the process of planned change and the role of strategic planning in developing the performance of institutions.

Study Methodology: The researcher followed the case study and used the individual interviews, documents analysis, e-mail, meetings notes and use of the purposeful sample.

Study Community: Two foundations have been selected from (4004) higher education institutions in the United States of America according to the classification of (Carnegie:2005) and according to certain criteria set by the researcher. The two foundations are lokenia and cober.

Study Results: The strategic planning helps the employees to understand the organization and its future commonly. This depends on several factors such as the trust between the dean and the college council and the trust between the management and the employees. And that the use of multiple frame pattern for leadership (political, bureaucratic, fellow and social) qualifies for a high level of integrity, uniqueness, flexibility and expands the participation circle.

4. *A study by (Alkhafajee, Byerman: 1995) entitled: "Total Quality Management and*

Strategic Planning in Academic Institutions."

Study Objective: Expanding the philosophy of total quality management to reflect the strategic time dimension for the performance of the foundation as a whole by relating total quality and strategic planning and integration of quality strategy in the components and goals of strategic planning.

Study Methodology: Analytical description and correlative approach are used.

Study Sample: Educational institutions in Britain.

Study Results:

- The development of strategic planning for universities requires the integration of total quality strategy in the components of strategic planning.
- The development of university mission requires its embedment with the introduction of high quality level educational programs, provision of services to the beneficiaries, encouraging research and community service and granting the opportunity for the students and employees for better participation.
- The development of the aims and mission of university necessitates the improvement of academic and professional quality in preparing the students.
- The process of evaluation of policies and planning procedures contribute to the knowledge of internal directions and a better analysis of the internal environment.

III. THEORETICAL ASPECT

A. *The concept of Strategic Planning*

Strategic planning is identifying the future trend of the organization and stating what it strives for through the surrounding environmental changes and taking the decisions related to identification and allotment of the required resources to achieve the strategic plans considering them as inclusive plan to achieve goals through a general framework that govern the policies of the educational institutions in different areas.

Strategic planning is considered as the beacon that guides the work of the organization and influences its survival, permanence, and development. Thus the higher management is usually keen on participating in it. Usually, the committee of strategic planning consists of all the managerial levels in order to ensure good preparation and implementation of the strategic plan. The strategic planning focuses on a particular activity or one field at a specific time. This is called as

short term strategic planning. It may also focus on all the faces of activity as it is related to the determination of long term goals in which all the managers of the organization participate in preparation. This type of planning involves all the policies related to all the activities. It also involves the procedures required to be followed and the rules that include the determinants of employees' behaviour and actions inside the organization. (Al-Sabaawee, 2003:6).

Strategic planning performs a basic role in determining the requirements for successful implementation of total quality as it acts as the mainstay and aid in facing the future challenges. Moreover, strategic planning provides no opportunity for speculations as every minor and major activity is subjected to study, research and analysis. Likewise, quality is considered as a long term stage that needs an integrated, highly precise and objective strategic planning. Planning includes key aspects starting from the previous knowledge of the institution, the current situation, what to be achieved and the foundation plans to achieve what it desires. (Alqazaz and Abdulmalik: 23:2004)

That the justifications for the use of strategic planning by organizations return to the complexity and interconnectedness of relationships and responsibilities and the multiplicity of factors and variables that affect the performance of the work. Thus the strategic planning becomes necessary to predict the future circumstances and prepare plans and programs to ensure the achievement of objectives in the light of the expected conditions; these justifications are represented by (Alhasan, and Alafif 13:2012)

A. Discovery of errors in the work of the Organization, namely failure to reach results consistent with the objectives set.

B - A striking gap in the performance of the Organization occurs when performance results are far from expected in relation to the objectives set

C - A new Director of the Organization is to run the organization in a way different and in style of leadership from the previous administration, resulting in a review of the set plans and programs

D- The need for administrative bodies to bring about radical changes in working methods and development and raise the efficiency and efficiency of human elements.

E. Strategic planning is a multilayer process that provides a scientific benchmark for the extent of achievement.

F. Strategic planning creates a democratic climate that allows the participation in decision-making.

1) *Characteristics and Advantages of Strategic Planning:* The Strategic

planning has many advantages that arise from being a qualitative development of different types of planning. Perhaps the most important characteristic of strategic planning is the following:

A. It is an integrated and diverse process for the formulation and implementation of the strategic plan, which creates the competitive advantage of the educational institution.

B. the Strategic planning starts from the comprehensive analysis of the current competitive center of the educational institution, and identify the current and expected opportunities and challenges, as well as the strengths and weaknesses of the educational institution.

C. Strategic planning is a multi-faceted process that transcends the traditional view, and it is characterized by objective thinking and insight into the future.

D. The strategic planning seeks to determine the future direction for the purpose of creating a competitive advantage, as it focuses on the production and supply of unprecedented ideas.

E. The Strategic planning achieves interaction and constructive dialogue between the three levels of planning (upper, middle and lower) so as to make decisions and facilitate the administrative process.

F. The Strategic planning contributes to supporting future decision-making methods in the educational institution in a scientific manner based on research, analysis, prediction, and comparison of different alternatives to the best decisions and the most feasible ones (Hafedhand Wahib: 2003,119).

G. The Strategic planning works to reduce the negative effects of the conditions surrounding the organization's activity, increase its efficiency and efficiency, and contributes to achieving a better quality of the product or service.

H. The Strategic planning seeks to develop the main paths of strategic action, which are less strategic plans and

formal, less stable, more change, and broader and deeper analysis of the traditional official plans that are close to the principles of the principles, rules of work, and stages of implementation.

2. *Dimensions of strategic planning:*

a. *Vision, mission, and objectives of the educational institution:* It is a general abstract idea close to the human dream, and a future perspective of the administration and its employees, which usually includes the broadest meanings. The mission of the university institution is the basic premise for which the university institution was found, or the core task of it, and the justification for its existence and continuity, which is a more detailed description of the activities, products, and interests of the organization and its basic values. The objectives are the ends that the university administration seeks to reach through the optimal investment of the human and material resources available, now and in the future. This is a guide to the work of the administration, to the extent that the organizational goals are realistic and express correctly about the forces and variables of the internal and external environment of the organization, successful design and implementation of an efficient and effective strategy (Yasin, 1998: 33).

b. *Strategic leadership:* It is the activity of the strategic leader in the field of decision making, ordering and supervision of others, using the official and informal authority that stems from the ability of the leader to influence and persuade in order to achieve the objectives.

It is necessary to have the conviction and belief in the leadership and the leaders of the minimum feasibility of quality and comprehensive, and the presence of enthusiasm and impulse required to provide the requirements to achieve because they form the focus of the integrated system to achieve the quality and satisfaction of the beneficiary and the rest of the parties concerned.

The success of the educational institution and its failure depends to a large extent on the adequacy of its administrative leadership (Jouda, 2004: 91). The success of the overall quality depends on the leadership's keenness to provide adequate material resources and training for development (Al-Qazzaz et al., 2001: 15) and that there is no shift towards total quality if the active leadership is not prepared at the different levels of the institution. Effective leadership requires the combination of wisdom, politics,

impartiality of intent and the acquisition of trust of subordinates and the care of teamwork (Al-Sawaf: 29, 1999), so it can be pioneering quality according to the following equation:

Leading Quality = Effective Leadership + Advanced Human Resources + Advanced Technology + Environment.

c. *Strategic environment analysis:* To keep educational institutions working in the competitive environment and competitive forces of government and private educational institutions, they must undertake strategic analysis by knowing their internal environment (strengths and weaknesses) and the external environment (opportunities, challenges or threats). Analysis (swot) contributes to the development of quality educational institutions performance. In order to know the quality of performance of these institutions, there must be dimensions to measure the performance of these educational institutions.

d. *Creative thinking:* In order to reach the leadership of educational institutions in the society, there is a need to coordinate and harmonize the general concepts of strategic planning (vision, mission, objectives, and strategy) for the sustainability of the pilot image of these institutions. As a key tool of quality, management leaders need to have creative thinking that contributes to high quality performance.

e. *Strategic decision making:* The Strategic planning is a significant component of the administrative processes of contemporary educational institutions. Its importance has increased with the expansion of the role of university education, the diversity of its functions, the inflation of its organs and the aspiration of its objectives.

These factors have had a significant impact on alerting governments and organizations in the various systems to rationalize their performance to achieve the ambitious goals of the work. "Therefore, strategic plans and future programs have developed that outline the direction and direction of implementation, coordinate its various parts, and define interim and final targets to be reached, (Ashour: 44, 1979).

The process of decision-making may be rational, logical, purposeful, and insightful if used in a discriminatory manner. It may be otherwise as follows in its first form: (Gnome: 2011: 2)

- a. Identify the problem or topic that is being investigated.
- b. Position analysis.

- c. Identify and manage alternatives.
- d. Think about the consequences of taking each of these alternatives and studying these results.
- e. Choose between these alternatives

This sequence assumes the availability of the elements of rationality, good judgment, and distinction, as well as the opportunity to reflect, reflect, and choose between alternatives. The factors that limit management's rationality include values related to emotions, emotions, the balance of power, group dynamics and personal factors.

f. Strategic planning as a tool for quality in university education: Strategic planning is a major reason for the existence of TQM because it is the main tool for TQM. It contributes to the transformation of educational institutions into institutions of high quality in their performance and has an effective role in overcoming the obstacles facing higher education. Quality in the administrative, technical and teaching work because it contributes to building an advanced generation depends on the community to build and develop the country with new ideas and creativity renewed. The educational institutions always strive to improve the level of services provided to the beneficiaries in order to keep them and stay with them and encourage them to be loyal to them and their outputs as well as to try to attract new beneficiaries. The satisfaction of the beneficiary is an indicator of the difference between performance and expectation, and the beneficiary builds his expectation based on his previous experience with the institution, besides the information and presentations by institutions to their outputs through the media (Aqili, 2002: 192).

Based on the above mentioned, the researchers believe that if planning is the heart of the administrative process, the strategic planning is the integrated plans that relate to the institution of higher education and the future translation of its strategic vision to achieve its future strategic objectives. And that leading activities in university performance contribute to making educational institutions to rethink how to use human resources and material more effectively, and how to compete in the labor market. And that change, creativity, and entrepreneurship have become terms of great consideration; it describes what successful organizations should do to survive.

Therefore, many factors influence the success of educational institutions when using entrepreneurial activities for the implementation of the pilot strategy. These include the ability of the organization to develop a vision, support the senior management of this vision, and the harmony of people in the work tasks in a manner that makes the entrepreneurial activities

flourish, sufficient to support entrepreneurial activities as well as the use of reward and compensation systems that enhance the pilot activities of leading teams and individuals, and encourage risk adoption. Fig. 5 shows how most of the literature-supported factors are within the design and implementation of the pilot strategy.

Fig.5 Pilot activities and implementation of the Organization's pilot strategy
Source: Kuratko & Ireland and Hornsby: 2001 "Improving firm performance through entrepreneurial actions: Acordia corporate entrepreneurship strategy" Academy of Management Executive, Vol.15, No. 4 p: 62.

B. Leading Quality

1. Concept: (Taima et al., 2008: 28) find that The increase in the intensity of global competition and the Japanese industry's sweeping of the global markets prompted the American institutions to develop the concept of quality leader, expand it by adding more comprehensive aspects and use advanced methods to improve quality and deal with beneficiaries and suppliers and the Quality to become a strategic control method on quality. While others felt that total quality is "a strategic input to produce the best product or service through productive innovation" (Philip Inxton 1995: 38). The US Federal Quality Institute defined it as "doing the right work correctly from the initial step while relying on the beneficiary's assessment of how well the performance is improving." In the educational sector, TQM is defined as "a strategic management process that is based on a set of values and derives the energy of its movement from the information in which it can employ the talents of the workers and invest their intellectual abilities at various levels of organization in a creative way to achieve continuous improvement of the organization" (Hixon, J: 1999: 6-24) Based on the above, many of the early writers and researchers have made significant contributions to the emergence and development of the concept of total quality. They presented a model that was the result of experience in the field of quality application, (Grosby) (Deming) and besides These prominent scholars have emerged from a group of specialists who have made clear contributions to advancing the development of concepts and ideas of overall quality (Malcolm Balridge, Feigenbaum, Ishikawq, Taguchi, Conway, (Al,a'aniand others, 23,2002).

Thus, TQM has evolved and expanded to become a strategic knowledge portal aimed at making radical changes in the culture of the educational institution and changing them from the traditional administrative method to the modern method capable of achieving a high level of quality and thus achieving success based

on satisfying the customer's wishes and requirements. (Alsawaf and Salih 2008:6).

Table 4: Common elements among the most prominent scientists of total quality Pioneers

Pioneers Standards	Walters	Deming	Goran	Grosby	Ishikawa	Baldrige
Leadership		*		*	*	*
Strategic Planning	*	*	*		*	*
Information system	*		*	*	*	*
Human Resource management		*	*	*	*	*
Design Process	*	*	*	-	-	*
Measuring and evaluating the quality	*		*	*	*	*
Focus on the beneficiary and satisfaction	*	*	*	*	*	*

2. Reasons for Interest in Quality Pioneers:

The researchers see that the Iraqi universities, including the University of Baghdad, face unprecedented challenges as a result of many of the changes that have occurred during the last few years at the local and global levels, namely:

- Increasing competition at the national and regional level in the field of education.
- Unprecedented progress in communications and information technology.
- The size and composition of the labor market have changed in terms of the entry of many foreign companies and their branches, which requires changing the qualifications of graduates such as skills, knowledge, and abilities.
- The need of the academic community and the business community for research that serves the objectives of academic publishing and helps in the development of organizations and institutions operating in the regional market.

3. Components of Pioneering Quality in University Education:

- An integrated strategic plan.
- An integrated system of policies that govern and regulate the work of the educational institution and guide those responsible

for performance to the bases, rules, and criteria of decision making.

c. Organizational structures that are flexible and proportionate to performance requirements and are scalable and adapted to the external and internal changes and challenges of the organization.

d. An advanced system of total quality, which defines the mechanisms of analysis of processes and the bases for determining quality specifications and conditions.

e. An advanced system for the development and development of human resources and the evaluation of its performance.

f. An integrated information system to support decision-making in the educational institution and to evaluate organizational performance, results, and achievements.

g. Effective leadership to lay the foundations and standards for the implementation of plans, policies, decisions, values, and ethics of work to achieve quality.

4. Quality Requirements for University Education:

a. *Senior management support & commitment:* (Low Sui Pheng 2004: 36) believes that the presence of outstanding management leadership that supports continuous improvement and is committed to total quality management represents the first step to the success of the quality system. The degree of vision and support of senior management provides a comprehensive quality environment and a critical factor for the application of TQM, in order to increase the awareness, interaction, and contribution of all members of the Organization. The importance of senior management is not limited to the allocation of the necessary resources but extends to the inclusion of a set of priorities by each organization.

If the senior management of the organization is unable to demonstrate its long-term commitment to support the program and achieve these priorities, it will not succeed in implementing TQM, and if the employees do not notice the effort of senior management, To a position that is not advanced, so the senior management should take it personally and guide and practice effective leadership, to ensure the success required in the application of TQM (Said, 1997: 92).

b. *Leading teams:* Al-Saidi (2008: 32) believes that the approach of participating in the practice of strategic planning works to prepare leaders for senior management, since strategic planning presents the managers of the functional departments with a kind of thinking and problems that can be faced when they are promoted to senior management positions at the university. It contributes to the development of inclusive thought and the integration of their sub-units with the objectives of the university as a whole. Team spirit and teamwork among the staff of the institution

and the practice of democratic leadership is the most appropriate model in the application of TQM. To set goals, make decisions, apply and expand the delegation of powers. Therefore, TQM provides leadership teams with managerial skills according to strategic planning including

- Setting measurable goals and paying attention to strategic planning.
- Strengthen teamwork as the foundation within organizations.
- Paying attention to appreciation and rewards when workers work effectively.
- Setting standards for monitoring and the need to use quality tools and processes while relying on the (Deming) cycle to improve performance.
- Encourage individuals to learn from mistakes.
- The ability to provide human relations and the subsequent delegation of authority.

c. Competition: Leading thinking involves naturalism by acting towards new opportunities. Kickul & Gundry (2002: 45) has found that the combination of proactive and activity is important, and the behavior of the organization must be directed towards a proactive goal. The organization is proactive and competitive towards environmental opportunities and presenting what is new and creative (Fox: 2005: 51). (Baremlan&Crant: 2000: 116) suggest that the organization can be proactive in providing new products and services to the markets, and with the first start to the market in providing a new product, if it follows the behavior of proactive measures associated with the following concepts:

- Take advantage of market opportunities that have nothing to do with the current operations of the organization.
- Offer unique products that differ from competitors.
- Strategic planning of the downstream phase of the product.

d. Independence: (Dess et al.: 2005: 427) believes that there are two methods for organizations using independence:

- Use work groups to accelerate entrepreneurial thinking: to help managers and employees work tirelessly, and use these groups to encourage the creation of new ideas, brainstorming about new ideas and adventures.
- Design structures for the organization that support independent work: Changing organizational structures may be necessary. Stable organizations with traditional structures can often not withstand competition. Their structures must be changed according to changes in their competitive environment.

e. Continuous improvement: Continuous improvement

includes both additional improvement and new cognitive knowledge enhancement as part of the day-to-day operations of the organization business units (AlJanabi, 2001: 68). Stevenson (2007: 417) states that it is a philosophy that seeks to improve all the factors associated with the process to turn inputs into outputs on an evolving basis, including individuals, equipment, suppliers, and processes. Training and continuous development are also seen as a means of developing the potential of individuals within their respective functions to achieve optimal performance, And that training is of particular importance because it is a series of organized activities designed to enhance the knowledge of individuals. The continuous improvement under TQM is reflected in the ability of the organization to design and implement an innovative system that continuously satisfies customer satisfaction through continuous pursuit of optimal performance through the realization of the following (Evans: 1997: 257):

- Enhance customer value by offering new products.
- Reduce error, defective units, and loss.
- Improve organizational response and session time performance.
- Improve productivity and efficiency in the use of all resources.

IV. PRACTICAL ASPECT

A. Description of the research sample on the strategic planning variable

This study includes the question of the statistical presentation of the results of the applied research with the analysis and interpretation of the results. The research determined the level of the answers in the light of the arithmetic averages by determining their belonging to each category. Because the scale of the research is the five-dimensional Likert scale, there are five categories that belong to the arithmetic mean. The class is determined by finding the length of the range ($5-1 = 4$) and dividing the range by the number of categories ($4/5 = 800$). Then adding it to the minimum for the scale to be categories:

($800 + 1 = 1.80$) which indicates a very weak tendency for individuals to sample the search.
(1.81-2.60) low
(2.61-3.40) moderate
(3.41-4.20) high tendency
(4.21-5) is a very high tendency

The paragraphs of the independent variable were divided into five dimensions: (Strategic Leadership = 7 paragraphs) Planning Operations Management = 10 paragraphs, objectives and mission = 7 paragraphs,

internal and external environment = 4 paragraphs, strategic decision making = 5 paragraphs 33) are divided into five dimensions. The following is an explanation of each of the dimensions of the main independent variable (Strategic Planning):

1) *Strategic Leadership*: The results of the statistical analysis show that the mathematical mean of the first dimension (strategic leadership) reached (4.1615). This indicates a very high tendency for the members of the research sample on the paragraphs of this dimension. (489). This indicates a strong homogeneity in the opinions of the sample of the research, which is confirmed by a difference coefficient (11.8%).

Table (5) Describe the Responses of the Research Sample to the Strategic Leadership Dimension.

First	Strategic Leadership	Arithmetic means	Standard deviation	Coefficient variation	Priority and Rank
1	The responsibilities of strategic leaders are clearly defined in job descriptions.	3.461	1.212	0.350	7
2	Strategic leaders envision or anticipate potential issues and opportunities and take appropriate initiatives.	3.692	.9830	0.266	6
3	Strategic leaders ensure that the actions required in their area of responsibility are carried out effectively and in a timely manner.	4.753	.6131	0.128	1
4	Encourages strategic leaders to work in team spirit and to co-operate with the staff to achieve the goals and objectives of the educational institution within their responsibilities.	4.153	.5924	0.142	4
5	Strategic	4.323	.6639	0.153	3

	leaders at all levels of the organization work with colleagues in other units of the institution to ensure the effectiveness of all functions in the institution as a whole.				
6	Strategic leadership leads and encourages and rewards initiatives by subordinates within clear and defined policies and procedures.	4.492	.7930	0.176	2
7	Feedback on the performance of subordinates is provided regularly and constructively to contribute to their personal and professional development.	3.953	.8556	0.2164	5
Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation for dimension		4.161	.48950	0.1176	

The results of the statistical analysis indicate that all the paragraphs have an arithmetic mean above the mean (3), noting that the highest mean was different (12.8983), which indicates the homogeneity of the opinions of the members of the research sample. The mean is greater than the mean and indicates a high tendency for the members of the research sample for paragraph (1) at (3.4615) and by the standard deviation (1.2129), which indicates dispersion of the views of the research sample.

2) *Creative Thinking of the Scheme*: The results of the statistical analysis indicate that the mathematical mean of the second dimension (Planning Operations Administration) reached (4.4831). This indicates a very high tendency for the members of the research sample to the paragraphs of this dimension and by the standard deviation (33892.) This indicates strong homogeneity in the opinions of the research sample. It is confirmed by a difference factor of (80%).

Table (6) Description of the Responses of the Research Sample to the Management Planning Operations

Dimension

Seco nd	Creative Thinking of the design	Arithme tic means	Standar d deviati on	Coeffici ent variation	Priory and Rank
8	A comprehensive strategic plan for the institution as a whole is developed that provides a planning framework for all sections of the institution.	4.4615	1.07641	0.241266	6
9	Planning is strategic, includes priorities for development and an appropriate approach to each work that needs to be done in order to achieve the best results both in the near and long term.	4.0615	1.01361	0.249565	10
10	Plans take into account, fully and in real terms, the internal and external environmental factors that affect the development of the educational institution.	4.5846	.91672	0.199956	4
11	Senior management facilitates the participation of direct stakeholders (beneficiaries) in different units of the institution, and exchange views with them at appropriate levels.	4.5538	.61316	0.134648	5

12	All those concerned are informed of the plans of the institution well, and to clarify the effects of these plans and what is required of various bodies related to the educational institution.	4.4462	.50096	0.112671	7
13	The implementation of the plans is monitored with the certainty of the extent to which the objectives are achieved in the near and medium term, and the outputs are evaluated.	4.8000	.59161	0.123252	1
14	Plans are revised, developed and adjusted with corrective decisions as required, in response to developments in implementation, structural evaluation results, and changing circumstances.	4.6615	.71320	0.152998	3
15	The plans directly link to information management systems that provide regular feedback for both routine (routine) and ongoing progress in the implementation of strategic	4.7538	.61316	0.128983	2

	initiatives, through key performance indicators and other data, as necessary.				
16	Risk assessment and management processes are an essential component of planning strategies, and appropriate risk assessment mechanisms are developed and minimized in case of occurrence.	4.1538	.59242	0.142621	9
17	Strategic planning is part of the annual and long-term budgeting processes, allowing for appropriate adjustments in the medium term as needed.	4.3231	.66398	0.153589	8
Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation			4.4831	.338920	0.075599

The results of the statistical analysis indicate that all of the paragraphs have an arithmetic mean above the mean (3), noting that the highest mean was in paragraph (13), which ranked first (4,800), indicating a very high tendency for the members of the research sample, With a standard deviation (59161.) and a difference coefficient (12.3252), which indicates the homogeneity of the opinions of the members of the research sample. The lowest mean is greater than the mean indicates a high tendency for the members of the research sample for paragraph (13) with (4.0615) and standard deviation (1.01361) and a difference coefficient (25%) which indicates dispersion of the views of the research sample.

3) Objectives, mission, and vision of the educational institution: The results of the statistical analysis indicate that the mathematical mean of the third dimension (goals, mission, and vision of the

educational institution) reached (4, 1956). This indicates a very high tendency for the members of the research sample on the paragraphs of this dimension and by a standard deviation (5, 16670). This is confirmed by a different coefficient of (12.315%).

Table (7) Describes the Responses of the Research Sample to the Goals, Mission, and Vision of the Educational Institution

Third	Educational institute objectives and message	Arithmetic means	Standard deviation	Coefficient variation	Priority and Rank
18	Strategic objectives are flexible enough to be modified whenever new conditions are created	4.49	.7930	0.176	2
19	Taking into account the strategic objectives of the University, the University must take into consideration the nature of Iraqi society and its culture	3.95	.8556	0.216	7
20	Strategic objectives achieve a balance between short- and long-term goals	4.46	1.076	0.241	3
21	The values that the university provides are generalized to the employees.	4.06	1.013	0.249	6
22	Relevant beneficiaries can see the University's vision	4.43	.9837	0.222	5

	and mission				
23	The University's mission is known to the employee at all administrative and educational levels.	4.55	.6131	0.134	1
24	Goals are formulated in behavioral terms and are precisely defined and clear.	4.44	.5009	0.112	4
Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation			4.19	.5160	0.1231

From the results of the statistical analysis it is noted that all paragraphs are very high inclination except paragraph (19), which indicates a high tendency for the sample to the paragraph, noting that the highest mean was in paragraph (23), reaching (4.5538), indicating a high tendency (13,366), which indicates the homogeneity of the opinions of the members of the research sample. The lower mean of the sample is greater than the mean means and indicates a high tendency for the members of the sample of the paragraph (19), reaching (3.9538) with a standard deviation (0.85569) which indicates homogeneity in the views of the research sample.

4) Strategic Analysis of the Educational Institution: The results of the statistical analysis show that the arithmetic mean of the fourth dimension (the strategic analysis of the internal and external environment of the educational institution) reached 4.2308. This indicates a high tendency for the members of the research sample on the paragraphs of this dimension and with a standard deviation (50449). This is confirmed by a difference coefficient (11.924%).

Table (8) Description of the Responses of the Research Sample to the Dimension of the Internal and External Environment of the Educational Institution

Fourth	Strategic analysis of the internal and external environment of	Arithmetic means	Standard deviation	Coefficient variation	Priority and Rank
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	the educational institution				
25	Documenting and discussing the environment in terms of its existence and work in it, and discovering those factors and trends that affect the way the management of its work and implementation of their roles in society.	3.4615	1.21291	0.3504	4
26	Clarify and identify the type of issues or challenges they face.	3.6923	.98303	0.266238	3
27	Identify organizational goals, and formulate a vision in terms of where you want to go.	4.7538	.61316	0.128983	1
28	Assess the strengths and weaknesses of the educational institution, as well as study opportunities and challenges in the environment	4.1538	.59242	0.142621	2
Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation					

It is noted from the results of the statistical analysis that all the paragraphs have a tendency (high - and very high) for the paragraphs of this dimension, noting that the highest mean was in paragraph (27) at (4.7538), which indicates a very high tendency for the members of the research sample, (12,198), which shows the

homogeneity of the opinions of the members of the research sample. A lower mean is greater than the mean means and indicates a high tendency for the members of the research sample for paragraph (25) (3.4615) and by the standard deviation (1.2129) Refers to the homogeneity of the views of the research sample.

5) *Strategic Decision Making*: The results of the statistical analysis indicate that the mathematical mean of the third dimension (goals and mission of the educational institution) reached (4.2830). This indicates a very high tendency for the members of the research sample on the paragraphs of this dimension and by the standard deviation (65908.) This is confirmed by a different coefficient of (15.388%).

Table (9) Description of the Responses of the Research Sample After the Strategic Decision-Making

Fifth	Taking strategic decisions	Arithmetic means	Standard deviation	Coefficient variation	Priority and Rank
29	The institution understands its positions clearly and in the long term, as well as can develop valid concepts about its work and build an illustrative framework for the implications of strategy development and implementation.	4.3231	.6639	0.153589	3
30	A better decision is made. Strategic planning provides a coherent, focused, and the accessible basis for decision-making so that results can be brought closer to the future.	4.4923	.7930	0.176524	1
31	Strengthen organizational capacity in terms of improving the fundamentals	3.9538	.8556	0.216422	5

	of leadership and strategic thinking capabilities, as well as strengthening behavior and strategic learning.				
32	Improve communication and public relations, since message, vision, goals, strategies, and actual programs can be effectively communicated to stakeholders.	4.4615	1.076	0.241266	2
33	Providing political support and support, where there is strategic planning that the educational institution will acquire legitimacy, strength, and support from the government and its organizations, and may be combined with and supported by law, administratively and financially.	4.0615	1.013	0.249565	4
Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation		4.2800	.70250	0.164136	
Arithmetic mean, standard deviation and total difference coefficient of the main variable		4.2702	.42450	0.099415	

It is noted from the results of the statistical analysis that all the paragraphs have a tendency (high - and very high) for the paragraphs of this dimension, noting that the highest mean was in paragraph (30), reaching (4.4923), which indicates a very high tendency for the members of the sample and the standard deviation

(17,652), which indicates the homogeneity of the opinions of the members of the research sample. The lower mean is greater than the mean means and indicates a high tendency for the members of the research sample for paragraph (31) at (3.9538) and by the standard deviation (.55569) to homogeneity in the views of the sample research.

B. Description of the Responses of the Research Sample on the Dependent Variable Quality Strategy:

1) Continuous improvement: The results of the statistical analysis indicate that the mathematical mean of the first dimension (continuous improvement) reached (4.4462). This indicates a very high tendency for the members of the research sample on the paragraphs of this dimension and by the standard deviation (30160). This indicates a strong homogeneity in the opinions of the research sample Coefficient of difference by (067833%).

First	Continuous improvement	Arithmetic means	Standard deviation	Coefficient variation	Priory and Rank
34	The University seeks to identify the causes of problems for continuous improvement	4.4308	.98376	0.222028	3
35	Management determines the requirements for continuous human and material improvement with a specific plan of action	4.5538	.61316	0.134648	1
36	The University relies on developing the skills and knowledge of the employees in order to improve the processes	4.4462	.50096	0.112671	2

37	The university administration relies on employee performance results as a basis for continuous improvement	4.3538	.48188	0.11068	4
38	The university administration adopts new programs and methodologies for continuous improvement to improve its operations.	4.1692	.99325	0.238235	5
Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation			4.4462	.301600	0.067833

It is noted from the results of the statistical analysis that all paragraphs have a tendency (very high) for the paragraphs of this dimension, noting that the highest mean was in paragraph (35) as it reached (4.5538), which indicates a very high tendency for the members of the sample and the standard deviation (61316) (13.465), which indicates the homogeneity of the opinions of the members of the research sample. The lower mean is greater than the mean indicates a high tendency for the members of the research sample for paragraph (37) when it reached (4.1692) and by standard deviation (0.238235) Accepted in the views of the research sample.

2) Proactivity and competition: The results of the statistical analysis indicate that the mathematical mean of the first dimension (employee participation) reached (4.4092). This indicates a very high tendency for the members of the research sample on the paragraphs of this dimension and with a standard deviation (46695). This indicates strong homogeneity in the opinions of the research sample Difference coefficient (10.59%).

Table (11) Description of the Responses of the Research Sample to the Extent of the Participation of the Workers

Second	Proactive and competition	Arithmetic means	Standard deviation	Coefficient variation	Priory and Rank
39	The University	4.707	.45836	0.09736	1

	works to predict the future needs and needs of society.				
40	The University has entered into new fields that competitors have not entered.	4.215	1.00766	0.23904	5
41	The University continuously seeks to study, analyze and address environmental variables.	4.2923	.82392	0.191953	4
42	The University applies a rigorous environmental examination that exceeds the work of competitors from other universities.	4.5077	.77304	0.171493	2
43	Precise thinking and proactive action are a university approach to leadership.	4.4923	.68746	0.153031	3
Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation		4.4092	.466950	0.105904	

The results of the statistical analysis indicate that all the paragraphs have a tendency (high - very high) for the paragraphs of this dimension, noting that the highest mean was in paragraph (39) at (4.7077), which indicates a very high tendency for the members of the research sample, (45836.0) and a difference coefficient (0.097364), which indicates the homogeneity of the opinions of the members of the research sample. The mean is lower than the mean indicates a high tendency for the members of the research sample for paragraph (40) with (4.2154) and standard deviation (1.00766) 0.239043) which indicates acceptable dispersion in the views of the research sample.

3) Pilot Teams:

The results of the statistical analysis show that the mathematical mean of the first dimension (employee participation) reached (4.4646). This indicates a very high tendency for the members of the research sample on the paragraphs of this dimension and by the standard deviation (49131). This indicates strong

homogeneity in the opinions of the research sample, Confirmed by a difference coefficient (11%).

Table (12) Description of the Responses of the Research Sample After the Pilot Teams

Third	Pilot Teams	Arithmetic means	Standard deviation	Coefficient variation	Priority and Rank
44	Setting measurable goals and attention to people with strategic thinking.	4.5385	.75160	0.165605	3
45	To promote pioneering teamwork as the foundation within organizations.	4.6923	.65962	0.140575	1
46	When new ideas are put into the team, there is a lot of interest in how to make use of them.	4.1692	.60128	0.14422	5
47	Team members excel in how much information they have about developments within the university as a whole.	4.6769	.61511	0.131521	2
48	Encourage team members to learn from mistakes and to ensure success in the work assigned to them.	4.3077	.55686	0.129271	4
Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation		4.4646	0.49131	0.110046	

The results of the statistical analysis indicate that all the paragraphs have a tendency (high - very high) for the paragraphs of this dimension, noting that the

highest mean was in paragraph (45) as it reached (4.6923) which indicates a very high tendency for the members of the research sample, The difference is 14.057, which indicates the homogeneity of the opinions of the members of the research sample. The mean is less than the mean indicates a high tendency for the members of the research sample for paragraph (40), reaching (4.0377) and standard deviation 1.03705; Scattering is acceptable in the views of the sample research.

4) Support and Commitment of Senior Management:

The results of the statistical analysis show that all the paragraphs have a tendency (high - very high) for the paragraphs of this dimension, noting that the highest mean was in paragraph (53) reached (4.5385) which indicates a very high tendency for the members of the sample and the standard deviation). 54558.) and a difference coefficient (12.683), which indicates the homogeneity of the views of the members of the research sample. The lower mean of the mean is greater than the mean indicates a high tendency for the members of the research sample of paragraph (50) reached (4.0769) and standard deviation. 81601), which indicates an acceptable dispersion of the views of the research sample.

Table (13) Description of the Responses of the Research Sample to the Dimension of Support and Commitment of Senior Management

Fourth	support and commitment of senior management	Arithmetic means	Standard deviation	Coefficient variation	Priority and Rank
49	The University believes in the need to implement the requirements of TQM in various university working journals	4.4769	.92039	0.205586	3
50	The department works to develop and disseminate quality policy and objectives among employees	4.0769	.81601	0.200155	5
51	The university administration	4.5077	.81246	0.180238	2

	on provides education and training programs on a continuous basis and in accordance with scientific foundations that achieve their effectiveness in achieving the best performance				
52	The University administration periodically assesses the performance of its activities and activities in order to reveal the area that needs improvement and development	4.0923	.72291	0.176651	4
53	The university administration seeks to mobilize financial and human resources and support for the implementation of TQM	4.5385	.75160	0.165605	1
Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation			4.3015	.545580	0.126835

5) Independence: The results of the statistical analysis indicate that all the paragraphs have a tendency (high - very high) for the paragraphs of this dimension, noting that the highest mean was in paragraph (57) as it reached (4.7231) which indicates a very high tendency for the members of the research sample, (68184.) and the difference coefficient (12.1325), which indicates the homogeneity of the views of the members of the

research sample. The lower the middle of the calculation is greater than the mean indicates a high tendency for the members of the research sample of paragraph (58) as (4.1385) and standard deviation (.68184) refers to acceptable dispersion in the views of the sample research.

Table (14) Description of the Responses of the Research Sample to the Dimension of Strategic Planning for Quality

Fifth	Independence	Arithmetic means	Standard deviation	Coefficient variation	Priority and Rank
54	Management wishes to grant independence in order to expand the innovation base.	4.2923	.52211	0.121639	3
55	The university grants powers to departments, units, and individuals working to promote creativity and innovation.	4.6000	.70267	0.152754	2
56	The University is working to give the teams more freedom to complete their work in the way they see fit.	4.2923	.55122	0.128421	4
57	Independence increases the ability of business units to learn about opportunities.	4.7231	.57303	0.121325	1
58	The University is working to exploit the strengths of each business unit in order to achieve leadership.	4.1385	.68184	0.164755	5
Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation		4.4385	.446410	0.100577	
Arithmetic mean, standard deviation		4.4120	.318820	0.072262	

and total difference coefficient of the main variable				
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C. The Correlation between the Main Variables and their Dimensions: Table (14) shows the correlation between the dimensions of the main variable, strategic planning and the dimension of the leading variable. The results of the statistical analysis indicate that there is a correlation between most of the dimensions of the research at a significant level (0.01), i.e., 99% confidence and (0.05) Trust (95%).

Table (15) Correlation Coefficients for Research Variables

Quality Lead	Conti-nues improvement	Com-petition	Pilot teams	Support of senior management	Independence	Quality lead	number	Relative significance	relationship
Strategic Planning	.471**	-.347-*	.686**	.357**	.419**	.338**	6	100%	excellent
	.000	.011	.000	.003	.001	.006			
Management of planning operations	.535**	.312*	.621**	.425**	.508**	.390**	6	100%	excellent
	.000	.011	.000	.000	.000	.001			
Educational institutes Objectives and message	.312*	-.109-	.460**	.267*	.324**	.246*	5	83%	Very good
	.011	.437	.001	.031	.008	.048			
Environemnt strategic analysis	.446**	-.309-*	.474**	.260*	.334**	.230	5	83%	Very good
	.000	.024	.000	.037	.006	.066			
taking strategic decisions	.377**	.267*	.680**	.293*	.406**	.267*	6	100%	excellent
	.002	.031	.000	.018	.003	.031			
Strategic Planning	.509**	.260*	.647**	.530**	.387**	.353**	6	100%	excellent
	.000	.0370	.0000	.0000	.0040	.0040			

There is a strong correlation between the dimensions of the main variables of the research for each of the dimensions (strategic leadership) and between (leadership teams, senior management support, and independence) at a significant level (0.01), and with continuous improvement and participation of workers at (0.05) despite Of the weak link between them, and this confirms the first sub-hypothesis: There is a significant correlation relationship between the strategic leadership after the variable and the leader of the quality leader and its dimensions. The results of the statistical analysis show that there are links between the management of the planning processes and all the strategic dimensions of the quality pilot, noting that there are correlation relationships at a significant level (0.01) and (0.05). After the objectives and mission of the educational institution had a share with five dimensions except (proactive) relationship was very weak, either after the internal and external environment has a strong relationship with all dimensions at a significant level (0.01 - 0.05).

D. Effect of the Variable (Strategic Planning) in the Variable (Pioneering Quality of Education): The table below shows that the results of the statistical analysis of the sample of the research show that the coefficient of selection (R2 = .276). This

explains that 28% of the strategic planning affects the quality leadership, while the rest is due to other factors. The calculated value of the test (F = 23.973) shows that strategic planning has an overall strategic quality effect, at a significant level (0.01), as it is shown in the table below.

Table (16): Effect of the Main Research Variables

Independent Variable		B	t	Si g.	R	R. 2	F	Si g	Dependent variable
		Strategic Planning	A	2.72	7.895	.000	.525a	.276	
	B	0.39	4.896	0.000					

It is noted from the above mentioned table that the fixed value (a=2.728) of the regression coefficient shows that there is an effect of some factors, which is explained if the strategic planning is increased by one unit (T) shows that there are a greater impact and significant differences between the variables of the research (strategic planning and quality pilot). This confirms the validity of the second main hypothesis: There is a relationship of significant significance

effect between the strategic planning in the Variable dependent of the quality lead.

Table (17) Shows the Analysis of the Effect of the Independent Variable in the Dimensions of the Dependent Variable

Independent Variable	B	t	Sig.	R	R. 2	F	Sig	Dependent variable	
Strategic Planning	a	2.332	4.492	.000	.548a	.300	5.056	.001a	Quality lead
	B	.132-	.417-	.678					
Operation management	B	.202	.904	.370					
Vision, message and objectives	B	.082	.413	.681					
Environment strategic planning	B	.235	.884	.380					
Decision making	B	0.090	0.599	0.552					

strategic planning, which explains the percentage of (18%) of the dimension of the leading work team, and the highest coefficient of strategic planning is 34% of the dimension of continuous improvement and proactively, the rest is due to other reasons, and that there is a significant effect at a significant level (0.01) for each dimension of the dependent variable.

The above table shows that the results of the statistical analysis of the sample of the research show that the coefficient of determination for strategic planning distance ($R^2 = .0000$). This explains that 30% of the independent variable affects the quality of leadership, while the rest is due to other factors. The calculated value of the test ($F = 5.056$) shows that there is an effect of excluding the independent variable strategic planning in the leadership of quality. It is also noted from the table that the fixed value ($a = 2.332$) means that if the strategic planning of the research sample is zero, the variable of quality leader will not be less than this value. The value of the regression coefficient shows that there is an effect of some factors which explains if the strategic planning increases (T) indicates that there are a significant impact and significant differences of dimensions (strategic leadership, vision, mission, and objectives of the institution, process management, internal and external environment, decision making). This indicates the importance of these dimensions to search for the variable. This confirms the validity of the second main hypothesis: There is a significant relationship between the dimensions of strategic planning in the variable leading quality.

It is noted from the table below that there is a coefficient of determination of the variable of

Table (18) Shows the Analysis of the Effect of Independent Variable Dimensions in the Dependent Variable

Independent Variable	B	t	Sig.	R	R.2	F	Sig	Dependent variable	
Strategic Planning	a	2.491	13.248	.000	.034	.183a	2.189	.144a	Pilot Team
	B	.161	-1.479	.144					
	a	2.832	5.056	.000	.113	.336a	8.008	.006 ^a	competition
	B	.369	2.830	.006					
	a	1.606	3.146	.003	.578a	.335	31.681	.000a	Continuous improvement
	B	.669	5.629	.000					
	a	1.699	2.778	.007	.474 ^a	.225	18.272	.000 ^a	independence
	B	.609	4.275	.000					
	a	2.502	4.878	.000					support of senior management
	B	.453	3.793	.000	.431 ^a	.186	14.389	.000a	

of quality assurance processes, and the ability to lead and implement the strategies of the university efficiently and effectively.

V. CONCLUSIONS and RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusions

1. Strategic planning is one of the administrative functions associated with the future of educational institutions. This concept emerged as a result of the adoption by the business organizations of the open system in the administration, especially after the global openness and the information revolution and the emergence of globalization and technological progress that led to the world becoming a small village. The organization as an entity affects and is influenced by the surrounding environment, and this mutual influence must be reflected in the formulation of strategies that adopt a change in the environment so that there is a compatibility of resources.

2. There are awareness and awareness of the importance of quality management processes in the educational institution Al-Hawtha (University of Baghdad), and knowledge of the strategies necessary to achieve it by the staff located at the top of the hierarchy below.

3. Continuous support and commitment to the importance of quality development by the Presidency of the University of Baghdad, and senior management.

4. The presence of teachers and administrators in the colleges of the research sample, with good knowledge

5. Provide an environment in the educational institution Al-Hawtha (University of Baghdad), which will promote creativity and appreciation of outstanding achievements, taking into account the changes that occur in the educational environment.

6. There is a near-universal commitment in the educational institution (University of Baghdad) to achieve excellence and excellence and to participate in the initiatives that help this excellence. The results of the analysis showed that there are very strong relations between the dimensions of strategic planning and the leading change in quality, except after the proactive Very weak with the dimensions of independent variable strategic planning.

7. The quality strategy is based on the strategic planning of the educational institutions of the university. It is a common success for the whole institution, which is very important for the top and bottom leaders and the community. It is a new set of rules and models for how to manage institutional and partnership building. The results of this research demonstrated the Strategic planning in general in a pioneering quality strategy.

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